

Appendix A. Supplementary Data

Supplementary Methods

Library and reference compounds

Remdesivir (Merck), K777 (BOC Sciences), hydroxychloroquine, PF-00835231 (Pfizer), PF-07321332 (Pfizer) were used as reference compounds with known antiviral activity against SARS-CoV-2. For remdesivir, the prodrug GS-5734 with CAS 1809249-37-3 was used in all experiments. Ponatinib (Johnson & Johnson Pharma) was used as a positive control for toxicity.

A compound library at Janssen Pharmaceutica consisting of 871,000 small-molecule antivirals was used for HCl-based screening.

Antibodies, stains, and buffers for immunofluorescence

Initially, cells were permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X-100 (Sigma) in Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS; Sigma) for 15 min at room temperature, blocked with 5% goat serum (Sigma) and filtered 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA; Sigma) in DPBS for 1h and stained with rabbit SARS-CoV-2 (2019-nCoV) spike monoclonal antibody (Sino Biological; 1:1000 dilution) or J2 mouse anti-dsRNA monoclonal antibody (Scicons; 1:2500) in blocking buffer for ~3h at room temperature in the dark. Subsequently, this procedure was shortened to 1h in total by performing all steps (permeabilization, blocking and primary antibody staining) simultaneously.

After primary antibody staining and washing, a secondary antibody mixture containing 0.01 mg/mL Hoechst 33342 (nucleic acid stain; Invitrogen), 1 µg/mL HCS CellMask™ Deep Red (whole cell stain; ThermoFisher), and either 0.004 mg/mL goat anti-rabbit polyclonal antibody conjugated to Alexa Fluor 568 (Invitrogen) or 2.5 to 4 µg/mL goat anti-mouse immunoglobulin M polyclonal antibody conjugated to Alexa Fluor 488 (Invitrogen) in filtered 1% BSA in DPBS was added and plates were incubated at room temperature for 1h in the dark. After secondary antibody staining and washing, 1% penicillin-streptomycin solution (Gibco) was added as preservative, the plates were sealed and imaged.

Toxicity assay

A549-hACE2 cells were seeded at a density of 4000 cells/well in pre-spotted 384-well plates (Cell Carrier Ultra, Perkin Elmer) with 100 nL of compound at a final starting concentration of 25 μ M in an 11-point dose-response format (serial dilution factor 3). After 24h incubation of the plates, 1-step ATPlite™ reagent (Perkin Elmer) was prepared according to the manufacturer's manual and added in a 1:1 ratio, followed by an incubation in the dark on an orbital shaker at 700 rpm for 2 min at room temperature. ATP-generated chemiluminescence was measured using the ViewLux™ plate reader (Perkin Elmer).

Supplementary Table S1. List of the cellular features that define the morphological profile of each

treatment

Cellular feature
Cell_CellStain2Marker_PearsonCor.mean
Cell_Marker_MedianInt.mean
Cell_Marker_SERHole_1.mean
Cell_Marker_SERSaddle_2.median
Cell_ShapeSize_Symmetry15.mean
CellCount_AllRetained_PerField
Cyto_CellStain_CVInt.median
Cyto_CellStain_SERHole_1.mean
Cyto_CellStain_SERValley_0.median
Cyto_CellStain2Marker_PearsonCor.mean
Cyto_Marker_SERHole_2.median
Cyto_Marker_SERRidge_4.median
Cyto_Marker_SERSpot_4.median
Cyto_Marker_StdInt.mean
Cyto_Marker_TotalInt.mean
Nuc_CellStain_SEREdge_2.mean
Nuc_Marker_SEREdge_4.mean
Nuc_Marker_SERRidge_0.median
Nuc_Marker_SERSaddle_2.mean
Nuc_Marker_SERSpot_1.mean
Nuc_Marker_SERSpot_2.median
Nuc_Marker_SERSpot_4.median
Nuc_Marker_SERValley_2.mean
Nuc_Marker_SERValley_4.median
Nuc_NucStain_SERDark_4.median
Nuc_NucStain_SEREdge_4.mean
Nuc_NucStain_SERHole_2.median
Nuc_NucStain2Marker_PearsonCor.mean
Nuc_ShapeSize_Symmetry03.mean
Ratio_Nuc2Cell_Marker_LogTotalInt.mean
Ratio_Nuc2Cyto_Marker_LogMeanInt.mean

Marker = LysoTracker™ Red DND-99; CellStain = HCS CellMask™ Deep Red; NucStain = Hoechst

Feature selection was done as described in the Materials and Methods. Cell count was added separately.

a. Reduction of staining steps and the effect on signal intensity, % infection and Z'

b. Titration of cell count and MOI

c. Titration of MOI

d. pIC50 of reference compounds in function of MOI

Supplementary Fig. S1. Optimization of the SARS-CoV-2-B1 antiviral HCI assay in a 1536 well plate

compatible for HTS. a Reduction of immunofluorescent staining steps. (Left) Description of each condition. Condition 1 is a standard procedure with separate fixation (Fix.), permeabilization (Perm.), blocking and primary antibody binding (1' Ab) steps. Condition 2 and Condition 3 are reduced procedures by combining several steps. (Right) Comparison of each condition with regard to anti-spike antibody signal, % of infected cells and Z' of % infected cells. Condition 3 was selected for the HTS assay. Infected control n= 96, uninfected control n=32. **b.** Exploration of cell count and MOI on % infected cells, Z' of % infected cells and cell count. To get enough infected cells, 3000 cells per well (c/w) were selected. **c.** Titration of MOI on 3000 c/w condition. For each MOI, the % infected cells, Z' of % infected cells and cell count were calculated. MOI 0.1 was chosen for the HTS assay as further increasing the MOI does not drastically improve assay robustness. **d.** The effect of MOI on the pIC50

of a set reference of compounds. Note that, compound potency lowers with increasing MOI. In addition to these parameters, the effect of different media types was evaluated on cell growth and infection (not shown).

Supplementary Fig. S2. Comparison of spike and dsRNA stain in A549-hACE2 assay. a,

Representative images of SARS-CoV-2 B1-infected A549-hACE2 cells treated with the indicated concentrations of remdesivir, non-infected control cells and infected control cells. Viral infection was measured by anti-spike antibody (red; top panels) or anti-dsRNA antibody (green; bottom panels). Blue, Hoechst (nuclei). **b,** Percentage of SARS-CoV-2 B1-infected A549-hACE2 cells as quantified by spike and dsRNA stains. Error bars represent the standard deviation of 2 independent experiments. **c,**

Antiviral activity of remdesivir and PF-07321332 against SARS-CoV-2 B1 in A549-hACE2 cells as quantified by spike and dsRNA stains.

Supplementary Fig. S3. HCI of SARS-CoV-2 Omicron BA.5 infection in HeLa-hACE2 and A549-hACE2 cells indicating syncytia formation in A549-hACE2 cells and less effective spike staining in HeLa-hACE2 cells.

Selected cell morphology features
 (Hoechst, CellMask, LysoTracker)

Supplementary Fig. S4. Analysis of cell morphological profiles for sim2nic calculation.

Morphological profiles are shown for PF-00835231 and ponatinib in HeLa-hACE2 cells infected with SARS-CoV-2 B1 for selected cellular features based on Hoechst, HCS CellMask™ Deep Red, and LysoTracker™ Red DND-99 staining followed by automated image analysis. These were then compared to the morphological profile of non-infected control cells via Pearson correlation analysis to compute a sim2nic score.